

FORMATION OF THE INSTITUTION OF PROCEDURAL FORMALIZATION OF EVIDENCE IN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS

Muminov Muzaffar Erkinovich

*Deputy Head of the Department of Criminal Procedural Law of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PhD in Law and Jurisprudence
(PhD)*

Annotation: In the article, the author studied the forms of bringing the case to court in the development of the criminal procedural legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, a retrospective analysis of the emergence and development of the legal norms regulating the institution of procedural formalization of evidence, divided into periods. The researcher tried to reveal the features of the historical development of the institution of procedural formalization of evidence by comprehensively analyzing the specific aspects of each period. At the same time, scientific opinions and opinions expressed by scientists regarding the level of socio-cultural, legal consciousness, and legal culture of different periods and the characteristics of the development of scientific thinking were analyzed.

Keywords: criminal proceedings, evidence, formalization of evidence, Zoroastrianism, Sharia, judgement, criminal procedural codes, history of the development of criminal procedural laws.

INTRODUCTION

In the legislation of many countries of the world, the case of every person accused of committing a crime has been expressed in a court of law, in public, and the requirement that he is not considered guilty until his guilt has been determined. This is to quickly and fully solve crimes by collecting, checking, evaluating evidence, and processing them according to the established requirements, strictly

following the norms of the criminal procedural law, giving fair punishment to every person who commits a crime, and exposing the guilty so that no innocent person is prosecuted and convicted, to ensure the proper application of the law.

This, in turn, requires the responsible officials authorized to conduct criminal proceedings to increase their responsibility in their activities related to the identification, collection, examination, and evaluation of evidence to determine the truth.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Although the procedure for the procedural formalization of evidence in a criminal case is described in the law, the issue of the formalization of evidence has a broader meaning. It is known to many that the characteristics of the society of a certain period find their expression in all systems of that period and society. Therefore, it is appropriate to dwell in detail on the content and history of the procedural formalization of evidence.

The modern essence of the criminal procedure was formed under the influence of historical conditions, including ethnic, cultural, religious, economic, and other factors, and emerged from different ideas about how to solve issues related to criminal proceedings, collection of evidence, and procedural formalization. All this has led to a variety of forms of procedural activity.

In the ancient states existing on the territory of our republic, the system of crime and punishment was regulated by customary law (VII-VIII centuries of our era) [1, p.56] and the main source of the Zoroastrian religion "Avesta" [2, p.66], and from this period until the invasion of Tsarist Russia, it was regulated by the rules of Sharia, which were instilled with the norms of custom and the views of the Islamic religion [3, p.5; 4, p.79].

The sacred book of the Zoroastrian religion "Avesta" is an invaluable historical legacy of the ancient culture of the peoples of Central Asia, the Near and Middle East, and it entered world history as an inexhaustible source of understanding

religious, legal, ethical, social and other worldviews. This rare historical-legal legacy provides extensive information about political and legal ideas of ancient times, the level of legal consciousness of people, social norms regulating property, family-marriage relations, crime and punishment, court and judicial practical issues [5, p.106]. The issues of crime and punishment are considered open and comprehensively regulated issues in "Avesta". According to it, the hearing of the case in court is based on controversy. Before solving the case, the guilt of the offenders is clarified in several cases, that is, the form of guilt – intent or carelessness, in a state of extreme excitement, confession of the guilt of the person who committed the offense for the first time or repeatedly, his religious affiliation [6, p.133; 7, p.214]. Testimony was used to determine these issues. Certain rules of testifying – the order of swearing in the "golden water of the oath" is established, and severe punishment for false testimony is defined [8, p.56].

So, in Zoroastrianism, during the trial of a crime committed by a person, he confesses his guilt or his guilt is proven through the testimony of witnesses. The testimony of the witness directly in the court, in turn, was shown as a specific form of evidence formalization.

In the process of historical development, Uzbekistan has gone through three stages of the criminal process. In the Middle Ages in the East, criminal proceedings were carried out based on Islamic law [9, p.65]. The judicial process in this period was distinguished by its simplicity, that is, it was not conducted in written form, the court session was discussed based on the oral arguments of the parties, and the decision of the judge was issued at the first session [10, p.543-547; 11, p.215-218]. Another peculiarity of this type of trial is that the defense is not present. It was a custom of the judge to make judgments based on religious law, that is, the Holy Quran, hadiths, comparisons and consensus [12, p.41-51], and local customs were not taken into account. The judge could not be based on his attitude or facts known only to him [13, p.37-38]. Fiqh (Arabic for knowledge, understanding, today, fiqh is

understood as Islamic jurisprudence, a branch of Islamic teaching that studies Sharia law) [14, p.483; 15, p.83] recognizes the following three types of evidence, and the guilt of a person is strengthened by 3 types of evidence, that is, confession – admission of guilt; shuhud – testimony of witnesses; Yamin – an oath [15, p.83].

For the Sharia court, the testimony of witnesses was the most important, often decisive evidentiary value. Most trials, both civil and criminal, require the testimony of at least two witnesses, and a person's guilt or innocence is established through the testimony of these witnesses. Only adult Muslim men with legal capacity could testify. Fiqh (jurisprudence) has paid great attention to the moral qualities of witnesses. Witnesses were not required to take an oath, but the witness was obliged to start the testimony with the words "ashkhadu" – "I testify" [16, p.367; 17, p. 30; 18, p.156].

As testified in "Hidaya", the rules and opinions about the testimony are summarized in the book. It covers issues such as accepting evidence, rejecting it, opinions between witnesses' testimony, evidence in inheritance matters, and witnessing evidence [19, p.2; 1, p.56]. The main thing that has the power of evidence for the court is the testimony of witnesses, documents and, in necessary cases, the clearing of suspicions conducted by the judge in secret or openly. The judge asked, "Is it possible to trust the words of the witness or the defendant?", "What is his character and mentality?" to find answers to such questions, he sends a written request to people who know him well or who can distinguish the character of people, sometimes he invites such people (at least two people) to an open court session. Giving testimony is obligatory, that is, one of the obligations of a Muslim, and it is impossible to avoid it knowingly [20, p.128-129].

At the same time, during this period, the criminal proceedings were conducted orally. Over time, during the Abbasid period, court records for civil cases were compiled. Confessions, testimony and oaths of the parties were considered the main

evidence. Testimonies of two trustworthy Muslim witnesses were recognized as full proof in the case [21, p.70-71].

Taking into account that the current legal system in Uzbekistan belongs to the "Roman-Germanic" family of law, it is appropriate to study the creation and formation of the order of gathering evidence, procedural formalization and strengthening of them with the ancient Roman law. In Roman law, a lot of attention is paid to restoring the violated rights of a person, i.e. returning to the state before the violation of the right. In ancient Rome, disputes between individuals, i.e. citizens, were tried privately by arbitral tribunals appointed by the parties. By the time of the Republic, the stages of the citizenship process were divided into two, in particular, the first stage "In iure"; the second stage "In iudicio" [22, p.46].

In the first stage, the magistrate determines whether the violated right cannot be defended through a court of law and appoints a judge. It also carries out organizational work related to the content of this work. *In the second stage*, the judge considers the content of the dispute and makes a decision. At this stage, evidence is collected, evaluated, and the case is decided on merits. At the beginning of the republic period, the court of recuperator appeared, which considered the cases between the consuls at the "In iure" stage, and later the cases between peregrines in a collegial manner. In Roman law, the trial proceeded on an open, free, and oral basis, and was carried out through relations of evaluation of the collected evidence. Testimony of witnesses, an inspection of the scene, documents and oaths were considered evidence. The plaintiff was required to justify his claim and provide evidence, and the defendant was required to provide evidence justifying his objection [23, p.81-82]. Before hearing the case, the judge distributed the papers with the praetor's formula to the parties and then began the discussion. The parties are plaintiffs, defendants and their lawyers. At this stage of the proceedings (in iudicio), the parties are not so bound by formalities, but are severely prosecuted for perjury and falsification of documents. Witnesses were also present at the court, and

expertise was also conducted if necessary. The judge's decision was final, after which it was not possible to file a lawsuit based on those documents. One of the greatest inventions of the Roman jurists, and one of the priceless values left to posterity, is the belief, i.e., inner confidence, gained by the free discussion of evidence, by the guidance of reason and conscience. This trust is not based on formal conditions, but on a rational and objective examination of all aspects of the case [24, p.33-34].

After the 1917 Russian Revolution, several laws and other legal documents were adopted in the judicial sphere, but there were no restrictions on the application of Sharia and customary norms by the judicial and judicial courts [25, p.13-14].

The Criminal Procedure Code of the RSFSR of 1922 [26, p.312-314], the Criminal Procedure Code of the RSFSR of 1923 [27, p.11-14] and the first Criminal Procedure Code of Uzbekistan, which was part of the former union, adopted in 1926 [28, p.13-16] include separate chapters devoted to evidence and reports, which are called "About Evidence" and "About Reports". They include the statements of witnesses, expert opinions, material evidence, reports of inspection of the place of the incident, written documents, explanations of the accused that should be used as evidence in court, issues related to the preservation of evidence, at the same time, should be reflected in the formalization of reports containing the process and results of investigative actions, circumstances, requirements for reports, etc.

Although the Criminal Procedure Code of Uzbekistan, which was a part of the former union, adopted in 1929 [29, p. 11-14] also has a separate chapter on evidence and its formalization, in this Code, unlike the above-mentioned codes, the chapter devoted to evidence is called "Collecting Evidence". At the same time, although the aforementioned codes have separate chapters for protocols, this code does not contain such a chapter. The collection of evidence, exactly what information is recognized as evidence, interrogation, seizure and search of the participants of the process, an inspection of the place where the incident occurred, the procedural order

of conducting these investigative actions, physical evidence, their storage and use issues related to inclusion and others are reflected in the chapter entitled "Collecting Evidence". But in the implementation of the proof process related to the formalization of the evidence, that is, the preparation of relevant reports and the requirements for these reports have not been expressed.

In the Criminal Procedure Code of Uzbekistan adopted in 1959 [30, p.25-33], the procedural actions related to the collection, assessment, and formalization of evidence, developed concerning the above-mentioned codes, are recorded. Chapter 3 of this Code is called "Evidence in a criminal case" and it contains the circumstances, evidence, their collection, evaluation, statements of witnesses, victims, suspects and accused persons, their rights and obligations, interrogation as a witness, which must be proven in a criminal case, the scope of persons that cannot be processed, physical evidence, the order and terms of their storage, reports confirming the working conditions, documents, expert opinions, etc. are recorded. In this Code of Uzbekistan, unlike the Code adopted in 1929, it is visible that more attention is paid to the issues related to the collection and formalization of evidence. This indicates that criminal procedural legislation has been improved in the historical development of our country.

Above, we have shown that in Muslim law – jurisprudence and Roman law, confession of guilt, the testimony of witnesses, and the oath of a person are used as evidence. However, in the Criminal Procedure Codes adopted during the Soviet regime, it is noted that confessions of guilt, that is, the testimony of witnesses are recognized as evidence, but it is indicated that a person's swearing cannot be used as evidence in the case [31, p. 69].

It should be noted that in the Criminal Procedure Code of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, which was adopted on September 22, 1994, and entered into force on April 1, 1995, a separate chapter called "General conditions of proof" was allocated, unlike the Criminal Procedure Code that was in force before

independence. It includes articles such as proof, proof participants, evidence collection, protection of the rights and legal interests of citizens, enterprises, institutions and organizations during the proof process, recording of evidence in the report, auxiliary methods for recording evidence, applications to the report, confirmation of the correctness of the recording of evidence, refusal of the signing of the report or confirmation of inability to sign, verification of evidence, evaluation of evidence.

The improvement of the general conditions of proof is being observed under the influence of judicial reforms carried out in the period of independence based on the new criminal-legal policy of the state, and the acceleration of the process aimed at strictly ensuring the priority of human rights and freedoms throughout the world [32, p.37].

CONCLUSION

As a result of the reforms in the judicial law implemented in our country, attention to the procedurally meaningful, correct and legal formalization of evidence in judicial investigation practice has increased. For example, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-5268 "On additional measures to strengthen guarantees of citizens' rights and freedoms in judicial investigation" of November 30, 2017, stipulates that it is not allowed to use an unknown source or a source that cannot be determined during criminal proceedings as evidence in criminal cases; from the testimony of the victim, witness, suspect, accused, defendant during the preliminary investigation, which was not confirmed by the set of evidence available in the court; except for the cases confirmed by the available evidence, from the information obtained from the testimony of the victim, witness, suspect, accused, defendant based on assumption, hypothesis or hearsay and, accordingly, does not have legal force, as well as the prohibition to use as evidence the testimony of a witness, victim, suspect, accused, defendant, expert opinion,

physical evidence, audio and video recording and other materials obtained in violation of the norms of procedural legislation.

In addition, the introduction of Article 95¹ into the Code of Criminal Procedure by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of April 4, 2018 "On introducing amendments and addenda to certain legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the adoption of measures to strengthen the guarantees of the rights and freedoms of citizens in judicial and investigative activities" solved the issue of inadmissibility of evidence.

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